

Health Practitioner Credential Fraud: An Emerging Research Opportunity and Critical Challenge

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Abstract. A recent scoping review on the role of AI in perpetuating or combating nursing credential evaluation fraud has revealed a critical need for collaborative research. Nurse credential evaluation is a key regulatory mechanism which protects patient safety and enables global nursing workforce development. The process relies on painstakingly applied human expertise in complex regulatory environments. Employment fraud is on the rise and nursing credential evaluation fraud has the potential to put lives at risk. Expert systems to augment human decision-making and streamline workflows are urgently needed. This scoping study details research opportunities to address a significant gap in the literature.

Keywords: Scoping review, Fraud, Expert systems.

1 Background

1.1 Nursing Credential Evaluation

Nurses, like many other healthcare professionals, are required to meet regulatory requirements in order to legally practice. This ensures public safety and quality of care. Nurse regulatory bodies are charged with ensuring that nurses have required skills before they are allowed to practice. When skilled professionals move from one part of the world to another, their professional practice may be regulated by different bodies and they may be subject to different requirements. When internationally educated nurses seek license to practice in a new jurisdiction, nursing credential evaluators review their qualifications and determine whether these meet a regulatory threshold to be licensed to practice in the new jurisdiction. Many innovative technologies such as blockchain and verifiable credentials are enjoying broader adoption in credential evaluation. However, this process is complicated by divergent educational systems, health professions, and roles within such systems [1, 2]. Credential evaluation is further complicated by widely varied sociotechnical systems: That is, credentials in one jurisdiction may only be considered valid if presented physically with appropriate seals and signatures, while other jurisdictions may have moved to fully digital, secure credentials. This sociotechnical diversity presents challenges for the blanket application of many cryptographic solutions. Credential evaluators are highly trained individuals with access to substantial archives of information reflecting the nature of professional credentials around the

world and guidance for comparing such features. Their work is critically important, as they empower skilled professionals to realize professional aspirations and facilitate efforts to address a global nursing shortage.

1.2 Nursing Regulation and Artificial Intelligence

Nursing regulators recognize the potential for artificial intelligence (AI) to create efficiencies and enhance workflow [3]. The United States' National Council of State Nursing Boards (NCSBN) recommends using AI to augment human decision-making [2]. A recent environmental scan cautions health system administrators and regulators to ensure that AI tools are systematically designed to be safe and effective [4], and to pilot tools before implementing them in high-stakes environments like credential evaluation.

1.3 Nursing Credential Fraud

Generative AI has been used to both perpetuate and combat employment fraud [5], and the authors of this study expect it is already being used to commit credential fraud. Credential fraud poses a significant risk of harm [6]. In 2023, the FBI and the Department of Health and Human Services disrupted a scheme to produce and sell fraudulent nursing credentials. Individuals who purchased these credentials were, in at least some cases, able to use them to obtain a license for employment in the field of healthcare [7]. The implications of such schemes are far-ranging for healthcare professionals, patients, regulators, educators, employers, and the general public.

2 Methods

2.1 A Scoping Review

This scoping review aims to map existing literature that addresses the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in both perpetuating and combatting nursing credential fraud. This scoping review was registered on Open Science Framework, adhered to PRISMA-ScR guidelines, and followed the five stage process outlined in Arskey and O'Malley [8]. The complete protocol is registered on Open Science Framework (OSF). Methodological details, including search terms, filtering processes, metadata, and complete PRISMA flow diagram, can be accessed at <https://osf.io/uahbmz/>.

Research Questions. We ask, “What is the state of the literature, through May of 2025, describing AI in perpetuating or combatting nursing credential evaluation fraud?” and “Are there empirical studies that offer evidence-based insights on these topics?”

Relevant Literature. We conducted systematic electronic searches for relevant peer-reviewed articles published before June of 2025 in five online databases: PubMed, ACM Digital Library, IEEE, CINAHL, and ASSIA. A combination of search terms designed to optimize the strategy were applied across the databases. Inclusion criteria

specified articles: (1) published prior to June 2025, (2) peer reviewed and published as scholarly literature, (3) written in the English language, and (4) addressing artificial intelligence in perpetuating or combatting nursing credential evaluation fraud. Exclusion criteria included conference proceedings.

Literature Selection. The first 25 articles retrieved were reviewed independently and results were compared to standardize the screening process, resulting in a 100% agreement rate. The two reviewers then screened the remaining articles independently for inclusion. All but four articles were eliminated during this stage (see Fig. 1). Full texts of eligible articles were obtained and rescreened by the same two reviewers. Both team members independently reviewed and extracted data from the four full texts which addressed nursing credential evaluation or AI-enabled fraud [9, 10, 11, 12]

Charting the Data and Developing Results. Both team members reviewed the full text of four publications assessed for eligibility and elaborated findings in a table using Microsoft Excel. The team collaboratively reviewed and summarized results.

3 Results

3.1 Publication Characteristics

A single publication addressed artificial intelligence in perpetuating or combating credential evaluation fraud, and none identified best practices for combatting nursing credential evaluation fraud. Each of the four publications was written from a different disciplinary perspective and published in a different scholarly venue. Each was retrieved from a different database (ASSIA, PubMed, ACM and IEEE). Two were scoping reviews written for health workforce professionals and did not address AI and credential evaluation fraud; the other two were directed towards more technical audiences and discuss recent trajectories of AI research and development for healthcare contexts, as well as challenges faced by regulators, policymakers, and others.

3.2 Themes

Uneven guidance for designing AI-enabled systems is available to nursing credential evaluators and nursing regulators. The UK, US, Australia, and the EU have developed research agendas designed to support evidence-based regulatory reform, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other such regulations support data protection, the AI Act and the Council of Europe's Convention on Artificial Intelligence, and the EU's Artificial Intelligence Act require transparency and risk mitigation [9]. However, oversight is limited and does not address fraud. AI takes a wide variety of forms, many of which can be used to enhance or to circumvent regulatory oversight. Meaningful distinctions among types of different forms that AI may take are not made clearly or consistently in the existing guidance relevant to credential evaluators, and so many guidelines are not actionable by credential evaluators and the organizations they serve.

Further research is required to design interventions for safe, reliable AI-enabled competency evaluation and credential fraud detection.

4 Discussion

4.1 AI Literacy and Credential Evaluation

Of critical concern is a severe lack of AI literacy among nursing regulators and credential evaluators. These individuals generally cannot make use of the extensive literature published in ACM and IEEE journals unless it is translated into non-technical terms and implications for perpetuating fraud, detecting fraud, streamlining workflows, and transforming regulatory processes are made clear. Guidance available to credential evaluators from professional associations rarely distinguishes among the many and varied types and uses of AI; regulatory guidance and policy does not distinguish between the use of AI for completing legitimate and legal tasks and for the perpetration of fraud. This leaves credential evaluators and the organizations they work for without a pathway to AI literacy, and without the expertise to know what types of AI literacy would be most useful.

4.2 Future Research

Technical guidance for the safe, equitable, effective use of AI-enabled regulatory systems that can increase efficiencies and augment fraud detection is critical. Nursing credential evaluators are specialists with deep knowledge who play a critical role in securing the safety of the health workforce. They perform the types of tasks that AI may streamline, but in complex and ever-evolving regulatory and socio-technical contexts.

The authors of this study urge researchers with expertise in explainable AI, rule-based and fuzzy expert systems, computer vision, retrieval-augmented generation, and other relevant processes to partner with nursing credential evaluators and regulators in research and development to develop human-AI workflows that produce efficiencies without compromising safety, equity, or transparency. For example, partnerships between credential evaluators and AI research teams might explore the accuracy of anomaly detection algorithms across existing repositories of credentials with associated human evaluation records. Existing legacy datasets would also enable research on the viability of document verification using computer vision across categories of credentials such as scanned physical certificates with signatures from diverse global jurisdictions. Development efforts may be accompanied by quantitative studies comparing performance, accuracy, and efficiency of human experts with that of AI-enabled systems; qualitative evaluation of AI-enabled outcomes; studies that explore the impact of bias in AI-enabled systems [4]. Trial solutions must be accompanied by evaluation research to measure the performance, accuracy, and efficiency of hybrid systems in context. The authors would be glad to develop collaborative research plans with interested parties, and additionally encourage interested research teams to connect with credential evaluators and with professional associations such as The Association for Credential Evaluation Professionals (TAICEP) to identify opportunities to collaborate.

5 Conclusion

Research exploring and guiding development of AI-enhanced credential evaluation systems with fraud detection capabilities are a critical and accelerating need in nurse credential evaluation. Partnerships between nurse credential evaluators, AI researchers, and regulatory experts must collaborate to develop effective AI literacy resources, validate opportunities for AI-enabled credential verification, and fill this significant gap in the literature.

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References

1. National Council of State Boards of Nursing. NCSBN's environmental scan COVID-19 and its impact on nursing and regulation. *Journal of Nursing Regulation*, 11(4S), S1. (2021).
2. National Council of State Boards of Nursing. The NCSBN 2023 Environmental Scan: Nursing at a Crossroads—An Opportunity for Action: Nursing at a Crossroads: An Opportunity for Action. *Journal of Nursing Regulation*, 13(4S), S1-S48. (2023).
3. National Council of State Boards of Nursing. Regulation 2030: First steps of a journey. *Journal of Nursing Regulation*, 8(2 Suppl.), S3-S52. (2017)
4. National Council of State Boards of Nursing. The NCSBN 2025 environmental scan: Going beyond. *Journal of Nursing Regulation*, 15(1), S1-S48. (2025)
5. Sriram, Harish Kumar. "Leveraging AI and Machine Learning for Enhancing Secure Payment Processing: A Study on Generative AI Applications in Real-Time Fraud Detection and Prevention." *Available at SSRN 5203586* (2024).
6. Draper, Michael et al. *Means to Counter Education Fraud: Legislation, practices and instruments. Volume 7* (2023). <https://www.coe.int/en/web/education/-/new-isbn-publication-means-to-counter-eduction-fraud-etined-volume-7> Accessed 30 June 2025.
7. National Council of State Boards of Nursing. The NCSBN 2024 environmental scan. *Journal of Nursing Regulation*, 14(4S), S1-S48. (2024)
8. Arksey, Hilary, and Lisa O'malley. "Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework." *International journal of social research methodology* 8.1 (2005): 19-32.
9. Lantero, L., Heleg, G., and Kulumzhanova, A. "Challenges and Practical Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Qualification Recognition." *ICCAA2-25. IEEE* (2025).
10. Lafave M, Amannejad Y, Mammadova U, Eubank B.. Systems that evaluate international equivalency in health-related professions: a scoping review with a focus on Canada. *Hum Resour Health*. 2023 Oct 6;21(1):79. doi: 10.1186/s12960-023-00864-y.
11. Jieyuan Liu. 2020. Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics Applications in Healthcare General Review and Case Studies. In Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Healthcare (CAIH2020). ACM, New York, NY, USA, 49–53. (2020).
12. Chiu, P., Thiessen, N. J., Idrees, S., Leslie, K., & Kung, J. Y. Nursing regulation in canada: Insights from a scoping review. *PLoS One*, 20(5) (2025).